

28-30 SEPTEMBER 2022

Data Compression and Cloud Screening using a High-Performance Embedded System-on-a-Chip for the Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation (EMIT) imaging spectrometer on the International Space Station (ISS)

D. Keymeulen⁽¹⁾, T. Pham⁽¹⁾, M. Klimesh⁽¹⁾, G. Allen⁽¹⁾, G. Flesch⁽¹⁾, R. Valencia⁽¹⁾, H. Xie⁽¹⁾, A. Kiely⁽¹⁾, D. Dolman⁽²⁾, K. Roth⁽²⁾, K. Crocker⁽²⁾, T. Whitlock⁽²⁾, C. Holyoake⁽²⁾, S. Burchfiel⁽³⁾, F. Kampf⁽³⁾, M. Kentley⁽³⁾, A. Robson⁽³⁾, A. Schepps⁽⁴⁾, B. Lazaravich⁽⁴⁾, D. Stoczek⁽⁴⁾

⁽¹⁾*Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology
4800 Oak Grove Drive, Pasadena, CA 91109, USA
Email: didier.keymeulen@jpl.nasa.gov*

⁽²⁾*Alpha Data Parallel Systems Ltd.
Suite L4A, 160 Dundee Street, Edinburgh, EH11 1DQ, UK
Email: support@alpha-data.com*

⁽³⁾*Correct Designs Inc.
122 Lenz Drive, Seguin, Texas 78155-7126, USA
Email: info@correctdesigns.com*

⁽⁴⁾*Mercury Systems, Inc.
3601 E. University Drive, Phoenix, AZ 85034, USA
Email: support@mrchy.com*

INTRODUCTION

System-on-a-chip (SoC) devices promise lighter, smaller, cheaper, more capable and more reliable space electronic systems. This paper describes the focal plane interface electronics – digital (FPIE-D) Xilinx Zynq-based data acquisition, cloud-screening, compression, storage and downlink computing system developed by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL), Alpha Data, Correct Designs and Mercury Systems for the NASA Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation (EMIT) instrument. EMIT is an imaging spectrometer that acquires 1280 cross-track by 328 band images at 216 images/sec. Following launch (14 July 2022), EMIT has been installed outside the International Space Station (ISS) and is collecting data from science targets in arid dust source regions of the Earth. EMIT will be used to study the mineral dust cycle which has multiple impacts on the Earth System. The science objective of EMIT is to close the gap in our understanding of mineral dust heating and cooling impact on the Earth now and in the future by determining the surface mineralogy of mineral dust sources.

The EMIT FPIE-D board design is based on a standard Alpha Data COTS Zynq7100 board in an XMC form factor. The FPIE-D Alpha Data hardware and components, including a Mercury Systems 440 GByte RH3440 Solid-State Data Recorder (SSDR), fit into a 280mm×170mm×40mm assembly. The FPIE-D peak power usage is 40 W. The computing element is a Xilinx Zynq Z7100 which includes a Kintex-7 FPGA and dual-core ARM Cortex-A9 Processor [7][8][9]. The COTS board was re-spun to make it suitable for space (replacing components with space grade equivalents) and to add features needed for the mission. The FPIE-D board is designed to be very flexible, and not specific to EMIT mission. The FPIE-D assembly with its Zynq SoC controls the other assemblies on the EMIT instrument. The FPIE-D Zynq Processing System is responsible for running the flight software, which includes command & data handling, command & telemetry with ISS over 1553 and science data downlink over a 7.4 Mbps Ethernet interface to the ISS. The Zynq Programmable Logic (PL) of the FPIE-D interfaces with the SSDR through a 3.125 Gbps Serial RapidIO interface. The SSDR alleviates the effect of two data rate bottlenecks in the FPIE-D System: data compression implemented on Zynq PL with a data compression (input) rate of 370 Mbps, and the data transfer to the ISS at 7.4 Mbps. The FPIE-D includes three processing elements implemented in the Zynq PL: (1) the Fast Lossless extended (FLEX) data compression block (a modified implementation of the CCSDS-123.0-B-2 recommended standard), which is providing 3.4:1 lossless compression (compared to 16 bit samples obtained after co-adding) and 21 MSamples/sec throughput; (2) co-adding capability of two successive images so that shorter exposures can be used, helping to avoid saturation of the Focal Plane Array during acquisition; and (3) cloud detection and screening so that cloudy images can be dropped prior to compression, saving SSDR space and downlink time.

EMIT MISSION

Figure 1. Arid Dust Source Regions

Figure 2. Mineral Dust Source Emission

EMIT is looking at the mineral dust cycle which has multiple impacts to the Earth System. The surface mineral dust lifted by winds into the atmosphere is the major component of atmospheric aerosols (Figure 2). The surface mineral dust sources are located in arid dust regions of the world (Figure 1). The science objective of EMIT is to close the gap in our understanding of mineral dust heating and cooling impact on the Earth now and in the future [10] by determining the surface mineralogy of mineral dust sources.

Figure 3. An example of an image cube of spectral light data set for an African mineral dust source region collected by EMIT

Figure 4. EMIT installed on Expedite the Processing of Experiments to the Space Station (EXPRESS) Logistics Carrier (ELC-1) of ISS

The EMIT [1][2] instrument is an imaging spectrometer: the images acquired by EMIT are three-dimensional data sets, where two of the dimensions are spatial and the third is spectral (Figure 3). These images can be regarded as stacks of individual two-dimensional images that capture the spatial scene. EMIT images have 1280 cross track samples (spanning 60 km on the ground) and 328 spectral samples, each viewing a distinct, narrow part of the electromagnetic spectrum (ranging from 380 nm to 2500 nm). For EMIT one three-dimensional image (or “frame”) includes 32 spatially coadded slices in the along-track direction, yielding an image size of 26.8 MBytes. Spacecraft that acquire spectral images that include hundred of spectral bands imagery spectroscopy) may have modest bandwidths available to transfer the data to the ground [3]; for EMIT the ethernet data bandwidth is an average of 7.4 Mbits/sec, and there is much interest in processing and compressing the data efficiently [4][5][6] before transmission. The EMIT instrument is installed outside the ISS on the ELC-1 (Figure 4).

Figure 5. An example of science acquisition of EMIT during one orbit of the ISS

Figure 6. Series of consecutive orbits showing typical activities with acquisitions of Earth Coverage Science Target

The instrument is acquiring two types of science data [11]. The first occurs when the instrument is above the science target during day time (Figure 5). The day-side acquisition consists of continuous observation over the science target

within an acquisition. Continuous acquisitions can vary in duration between 35 seconds and 11 minutes. Typical operations include between 0 and 23 acquisitions per orbit. The second type of science acquisitions are dark calibrations. Since EMIT does not have an on-board calibration source it relies on dark calibration when the instrument is over the ocean at night.

FPIE-D AVIONICS AND DATA PROCESSING

Figure 7. FPIE-D processor Print Wiring Board (PWB)

Figure 9. FPIE-D Assembly with SSSR and SpaceVPX Backplane

Figure 8. EMIT instrument mounted on Vibration Plate

The EMIT FPIE-D board design is based on a standard Alpha Data COTS Zynq7100 board in an XMC form factor [14] (Figure 7). The COTS board was re-spun to make it suitable for space (replacing components with space grade equivalents where needed), and to add features needed for the EMIT mission that were not available on the COTS product. Since the Zynq is not space qualified, JPL screened Zynq parts to find chips best suitable for the EMIT mission. The FPIE-D design mitigates for Zynq Processing System (PS) single event upsets (SEUs) by disabling the Zynq L1 and L2 ARM processor caches (via software) and mitigates for single event latch-up (SEL) states by monitoring the Zynq Auxiliary current and automatically performing a power-on-reset of the Zynq SoC via board circuitry (ProASIC FPGA) to clear the SEL state. Finally, the FPIE-D board uses a ProASIC to monitor the Zynq PS state (via detection of a software-generated heartbeat), to provide Zynq resets and to switch QSPI Zynq configuration image selection when rebooting is required.

The FPIE-D assembly with its Zynq SoC, controls the other assemblies on the EMIT instrument (Figure 8). The assemblies include: (1) the Power Conditioning Electronics (PCE) for transforming the 110V from the ISS to +28V power rails to other EMIT assemblies; (2) the High Power – Lower Cost Control Electronics (HP-LCCE) for interfacing with the cryocooler to maintain -120degC temperature for the Focal Plane Array (FPA); (3) the Focal Plane Interface Electronics - Analog (FPIE-A) for configuring the FPA and reading the Voltage from the FPA which is transformed into digital data with very low noise; (4) the Power Supply Unit (PSU) for providing low noise power rails to the FPIE-A and FPA; (5) the Analog Thermostat and Motor controller (ATOM) for providing heating controls and temperature telemetry of the spectrometer and the assemblies on the electronics mounting plate; and (6) the PCE Interface and Telemetry Box (PITB) for providing telemetry from the PCE such as voltages and currents. In addition, the FPIE-D Zynq PS is responsible for running the flight software, which includes command & data handling (C&DH), command & telemetry with ISS over 1553 and science data downlink over 7.4 Mbps Ethernet interface to the ISS. The Zynq Programmable Logic (PL) of the FPIE-D interfaces with the SSSR through a 3.125 Gbps Serial RapidIO (SRIO) [12].

FPIE-D DATA PROCESSING

The FPIE-D includes a processor board and a Solid-State Data Recorder (SSDR) (Figure 9). The SSSR is a 440 GBytes RH3440 SSSR from Mercury Systems. It is a 3U VPX form-factor with 4-lane Serial RapidIO (SRIO) interface providing 1160 Mbytes/sec data rate.

Figure 10. The FPPIE-D includes a space processor board with the Zynq 7Z100 designed by Alpha Data and RH3440 SSSDR from Mercury Systems [12]. The high performance functions of the FPPIE-D are implemented on the Zynq PL and the Zynq PL data flow is orchestrated by the Zynq PS.

Figure 11. FLEX is a predictive compressor with a closed-loop quantization step that allows either lossless or near-lossless compression

It is based on a radiation-tolerant flash RTG4 FPGA that provides an SRIO interface, the error correction for NAND Flash Array and the management of NAND Bad block table. It has also a Magnetic RAM (MRAM) chip to identify the bad block in the NAND Flash. The SSSDR allows handling of two data rate bottlenecks of the FPPIE-D System (Figure 10). The first bottleneck is the data compression implemented on Zynq PL. The data compression (input) rate is 370 Mbps while the data rate from the FPPIE-A is 1.6 Gbps. This bottleneck is resolved by saving the data from the FPPIE-A on the SSSDR (in a region designated as the “Raw Image Data partition” shown as “High Speed Buffer” on Figure 10), then reading back the data as needed for compression. The second bottleneck is the data transfer to the ISS at 7.4 Mbps. This bottleneck is resolved by saving the compressed data to the SSSDR (in a region designated as the “Compressed Image Data partition” shown as “Data Storage” on Figure 10), then reading back the data as needed for transmission.

The science data flow through the FPPIE-D has 3 steps (Figure 10). During acquisition, FPPIE-D collects the acquisition image data from the FPA through the FPPIE-A at 1.6 Gbps, overlays ancillary information related to the image into the first band of the image then stores the data in the SSSDR Raw Image Data partition. During processing, the FPPIE-D reads the Raw Image Data partition data, then performs co-adding, right-shifting, cloud screening, compressing and packetization, before storing the data to the Compressed Image Data partition. During downlink, the FPPIE-D reads from the Compressed Image Data partition and sends it to the ISS via the Ethernet interface. On a given orbit, the EMIT avionics will perform one of more of these activities (Figure 6): data acquisition and storage, data processing and storage (continuously while there is data on the Raw Image Data partition and when data acquisition is not executing) and data downlinking (continuously while there is data in the Compressed Image Data partition even during acquisition and processing).

The FPPIE-D processing consists of the following 3 elements. First, it includes the Fast Lossless extended (FLEX) data compression block [13], which provides EMIT during In-Orbit-checkout (IOC) phase of the mission lossless compression ratio of 2.98:1 (compared to 14 bit samples obtained after co-adding and dropping 3 least significant bits) and a data throughput of 21 MSamples/sec. Both the compression ratio and data throughput performance are needed to accommodate the on-board SSSDR storage and ISS Ethernet downlink constraints. The JPL-developed “Fast Lossless Extended” (FLEX) hyperspectral compressor is a low complexity compression technique (Figure 11) designed specifically for lossless and near-lossless compression of multi- and hyperspectral imagery. It is based on Fast Lossless (FL) compressor that forms the basis of CCSDS recommended standards 123.0-B-1 (Lossless) and 123.0-B-2 (Low-Complexity Lossless and Near-Lossless) for multi- and hyperspectral imagery. The EMIT platform uses the algorithm implemented in the Zynq PL. On EMIT, each FLEX compression FPGA core operates on one “co-added frame” at a time, where a co-added frame consists of 1280 cross-track pixels by 328 spectral band by 32 co-added images. The FLEX compression core Data Flow block diagram is shown in Figure 12. The data flows between the 3 arithmetic modules implementing the core of the compressor. The predictor quantizer block computes the context $c_z(t)$ and the mapped quantizer index $\delta_z(t)$. The weight update block calculates the weight vector for each sample. The entropy encoder block produces the compressed image data. The uncompressed, compressed, and intermediary data are provided by the internal memories and internal FIFOs which interface with the two external DDR3 memories. The predictor, the weight update and the entropy encoder blocks are pipelined: when the predictor is working on sample index $t+1$, the weight-update and the entropy encoder are working on the sample index t . The compression initialization data used by the weight update and the predictor quantizer block are programmable through C&DH command.

Figure 12. FLEX Compression core Data Flow Control Block Diagram

EMIT can also use on-board default values for the compression initialization data, obtained through optimization using AVIRIS-NG data sets on the ground. The FPGA implementation of the FLEX compressor has 3 compression cores working in parallel. The implementation achieves a throughput of 21 MSamples/sec when using all 3 compression cores. The implementation supports input images with sample dynamic range up to 18 bits/sample, but on EMIT the images compressed have 14 bit samples. Data throughput includes the time to upload the frames from the SSSDR to the board SDRAM DDR3, co-adding, right-shifting, cloud screening, transforming from BIL to BIP scan order, compression and then storing the compressed segments from the board SDRAM DDR3 to SSSDR.

The second element of the FPIE-D processing provides co-adding capability of the signal from each of two consecutive 30 m along-track samples so that shorter exposures can be used, helping to avoid saturation of the Focal Plane Array during acquisition. The third element of the FPIE-D processing provides cloud detection and screening so that cloudy images can be discarded prior to compression, saving SSSDR space and downlink time. During an early portion of the EMIT IOC phase of the mission, 10% of the images were flagged as cloudy. Cloud detection compares the values in five bands of each pixel against specified thresholds to determine whether the pixel is cloudy. Any frame containing more cloudy pixels than a specified threshold is dropped by and does not undergo compression or writing to the SSSDR Compressed Image Data partition. The band selection and the bands and frame thresholds are programmable. The mission initial thresholds are based on data collected by the AVIRIS and AVIRIS-NG airborne imaging spectrometers combined with calibration of the EMIT instrument during thermal vacuum testing.

FPIE-D SW/FW ARCHITECTURE

Figure 13. FPIE-D Zynq-7000 hardware architecture, and FPGA design (PL).

Figure 14. FPIE-D Application Flight software architecture

The EMIT flight software runs on just one of the two Zynq ARM cores, with L1 caches and L2 cache disabled for SEU mitigation. The other core is unused. The architecture of the FPIE-D portion of the software has 3 layers (Figure 14): Application FSW High level which let separate the mission specific code from control of the hardware, the Hardware Abstraction layer which let us switch operating systems of target board and driver and OS Layer which separate the kernel

code from application code. The hardware layer is implemented in the FPGA and on the board. The separation of layers allows the development effort to be distributed while allowing the designs to be easily re-targeted to existing or new modules. The FPGA design is divided into many sub-modules, each concerned with a single task typically controlled by registers accessed by software running on the ARM core(s) (Figure 13). The “data flows” in the firmware (FW) design are steered by software (SW) via control registers. Interrupts are used from the Zynq PL to signal software threads (running on the Zynq PS) when operations complete or when FW is ready for a new task.

Figure 15. FPIE-D Threading model supporting Virtual Process (RTP in VxWorks)

Figure 16. Multi Partition Recorder (MPR) API and SSD DMA IP

The threading philosophy is based on cooperative multi-tasking (Figure 15). The main processing pipeline is defined with modular threads. Each class housing a thread, is either a Source, a Sink, or a Source and a Sink in the FPGA. Any source can be attached to any sink. Each thread performs one tasks on the pipeline which consists mainly to just steering the data in the FPGA which does the processing work such that the thread sleeps most of the time. With this architecture the state of the pipeline can be dynamically change without re-compiling the application. The Application Flight Software is designed to run as a Virtual Process (RTP in VxWorks) which provides protection from self, and to the Kernel: if something goes wrong due to wrong command sequence uploaded or SEU, the C&DH kills the RTP, and restart it. This process will clean up all the memory, and threads safely, restart the application, and reconfigure the FPGA design. Although this capability was available to C&DH, it was not used when Application FSW was integrated with C&DH and was replaced with the option to exercise a Power-on-Reset (POR) of the Zynq with a reboot of C&DH with limited thermal impact on the instrument.

The DMA IP and Multi partition recorder (MPR) API provides a simple file system to interact with the drive. The disk is divided into 2 partitions treated as circular buffers. The partitions are presented to the C&DH with 4 access methods: write, read, erase, and traverse meta data entries. The writes are appending operations adding to the data stored in the partition. The reads can be to any part of the valid data in the partition. The erases are always from the start of the oldest data. The API looks like a file that can be appended to, has a seek-able read pointer, and can be truncated from the start of. As space is freed from erases, it becomes available for writing to due to the circular nature of its implementation. The partition has also the option (used on EMIT) to auto erase when full.

The complexity of the design was mitigated by designing for debugging using VxWorks IDE based interactive software debugger (over Ethernet or Serial), and Xilinx XSDK/Vitis SDK interactive debugging (over JTAG). In addition, the design includes a menu-based ground system (GSE) mode for testing; debug mode builds; test cases (production testing, hammer testing and application testing); and FPGA debugging with ILA insertion. Finally, for the Zynq PL, JPL used an ARM AXI/OCF BFM to quickly write (and run) write/read based testcases developed by Alpha Data and Correct Designs. The testcases utilized an enhanced VHDL environment using OSVVM library components and migrated from Xsim to Questa, added Vivado Tcl scripts to automatically build and run regressions from the command line using a configurable, automated regression environment.

FPIE-D STATUS

Some statistics have been compiled for a portion of the IOC period. From August 13, 2022 to September 5 (22 days), the EMIT FPIE-D acquired and processed over 200974 frames, which is a total of 10.8 TeraBytes of raw data (before co-adding). After co-adding, cloud screening and compression this corresponded to 1.4 TeraBytes of data, which has been downlinked, and this became a total of 4.2 TeraBytes of science data on the ground after decompression.

Figure 17. File Size Histogram of cloud screened and compressed data

The coverage map for the downlinked data is shown in Figure 17. The co-added frames acquired can be classified into 6 categories from a cloud screening and compression perspective: frames dropped due to being deemed cloudy (11.8% of the frames), dark acquisition over the ocean (average compression ratio of 5:1), science acquisition over water (compression ratio 4.4:1), science acquisition with no clouds (compression ratio 3.4:1), and science acquisition with clouds (compression of 2.8:1). (Compression ratios are for co-added images and based on the original stored size of 16 bits per sample.)

Figure 18. EMIT First Light in Western Australia 28 July 2022 02:51 UTC and acquired scenes of spectral light data (blue squares made of 1280 cross-track by 1280 along track co-added pixels) until August 21, 2022.

EMIT was launched with SpaceX ISS Commercial Resupply Service (CRS-25) using SpaceX Cargo Dragon 2 C208 S/C with Falcon 9 rocket, Tuesday July 14th, 2022. The EMIT clouds screening scene of 1280 by 1280 co-added samples shows 5 frames of 32 by 1280 co-added pixels (black lines) marked as cloudy and not stored on the SSDR. The EMIT dust source region in Saudi Arabia shows a typical source region with a compression ratio of 3:4:1.

CONCLUSION

The Earth Venture Instrument, Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation has collected its first imaging spectroscopy measurements on July 28, 2022. To achieve this milestone, EMIT FPIE-D high-performance embedded computing SoC Hardware, Application Software and Application Firmware has performed acquisition of images of spectral light data at 1.6 Gbit/sec, processing (Co-adding, Right Shift, Clouds Computation and Clouds Screening) and downlink using Mercury SSDR and Alpha Data double partition and journaling Multi Partition Recorder (MPR) API Software and DMA IP FPGA technology to provide the first spectral data of 1280 cross track by 328 bands. This was made possible through the integration of new space technologies such as Xilinx Zynq 7z100 System-on-Chip (with 2 ARM Cortex-A9 processors operating 800 MHz Clock, 1 Kintex-7 FPGA and multiple hard-core interfaces (UART,

ETH, SPI)), 3D PLUS DDR3, 3D PLUS Radiation Intelligent Memory Controller (RIMC), fast data rate SpaceVPX inter-boards connector, Serial RapidIO communication protocol IP, 8Gb/s data rate 440 GBytes Space SDDR from Mercury Systems, Single Assembly providing C&DH and Application FSW/Firmware for the full instrument including SDDR, Radiation Tolerant Hardware using SW/FW/System SEE mitigation (L1/L2 Cache disable, not use OCM, SEM IP (Scrubbing), Xilinx AXI bus firewall), Modular OS/Software/Firmware architecture and on-board data processing. Over 22 days of the EMIT IOC phase of the mission, the FPIE-D on-board data processing which includes co-adding, clouds screening and data compression has provided 4.2 TeraBytes of science data representing more than 10.8 TeraBytes acquired.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work described here would not have been possible with only the contributions of those listed as co-authors. Thanks must be given to Thomas Werne, Josh Schoolcraft, Ryan White, Rick Purcell, Michael Bernas and Elliott Liggett, for the integration of the FPIE-D Hardware, Software and Firmware with the EMIT avionics and EMIT instrument resolving challenging issues during the integration. The authors would like to thank the EMIT Integration and Test (I&T), System Engineering, IOS, SDDS and Science teams for integrating and testing the full flight instrument and for deploying and operating successfully EMIT into space as well as the JPL offices (Mission Assurance, manufacturing and packaging, parts engineering, contract, shipping/receiving, import/export) supporting flight missions which were essential for the success of the FPIE-D. The authors would also like to acknowledge Rob Green, EMIT PI, Charlene Ung, EMIT project manager, Randy Pollock, EMIT instrument manager, Ben Bornstein and Violet Torossian, EMIT Avionics delivery organization leads, Arbi Karapetian, Nelson Alhambra, Sam Dolinar, Anil Thakoor and Jason Gates, FPIE-D delivery organization leads, for their leadership during the development, testing and integration of the FPIE-D hardware, firmware and software to the EMIT avionics and EMIT full instrument. A thank you is also owed to a number of the ISS Program technical staff members for helping the EMIT team gain insight into the ISS data downlink management architecture. The authors gratefully acknowledge NASA and the Earth System Science Pathfinder program office as well as the broad set of contributors to the EMIT mission. The research was carried out at the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, under a contract with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (80NM0018D0004). © 2021. California Institute of Technology. Government sponsorship acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] EMIT Web site: <https://earth.jpl.nasa.gov/emit/>
- [2] Green, Robert O., Natalie Mahowald, Charlene Ung, David R. Thompson, Lori Bator, Matthew Bennet, Michael Bernas et al. "The Earth Surface Mineral Dust Source Investigation: An Earth Science Imaging Spectroscopy Mission.", in IEEE Aerospace 2020.
- [3] Committee on the Decadal Survey for Earth Science and Applications from Space, Space Studies Board, "Thriving on Our Changing Planet: A Decadal Strategy for Earth Observation from Space", The National Academies Press, 2018.
- [4] D. Keymeulen, H. Luong, T. Pham, A. Kiely, M. Klimesh, M. Cheng, D. Dolman, C. Holyoake, K. Crocker, "Hardware implementation of Lossless and Lossy Compression of Space-based Multispectral and Hyperspectral Imagery," in Proceedings of 2016 HypSIRI Science and Applications Workshop, 18 - 20 October 2016, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA.
- [5] Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS), Lossless Data Compression, Recommendation for space data system standards vol. 121.0-B-1: CCSDS, 1997. (<http://public.ccsds.org>)
- [6] C. Hartzell, L. Graham, T. Tao, H. Goldberg, J. Carpena-Nunez, D. Racek, C. Taylor, C. Norton, "Data System Design for a Hyperspectral Imaging Mission Concept," in Proceedings of IEEE Aerospace Conference 2009.
- [7] E. Blem, J. Menon, and K. Sankaralingam, Detailed Analysis of Contemporary ARM and x86 Architectures, Technical report, University of Wisconsin - Madison, 2013.
- [8] N. Mehta, Xilinx 7 Series FPGAs: The Logical Advantage, Xilinx WP405, 2012.
- [9] Zynq-7000 SoC Technical Reference Manual Xilinx: https://www.xilinx.com/support/documentation/user_guides/ug585-Zynq-7000-TRM.pdf (UG585 (v1.13), April 2, 2021)
- [10] Longlei Li, Natalie M. Mahowald, Yves Balkanski, Paul Ginoux, Maria Goncalves Ageitos, Robert O. Green, Douglas S. Hamilton, Olga Kalashnikova, Martina Klose, Jasper F. Kok, Ron L. Miller, Vincenzo Obiso, David Paynter, Carlos Perez Garcia-Pando, David R. Thompson, "Quantifying the range of the dust direct radiative effect due to source mineralogy uncertainty", In Atmos. Chem. Phys. , 21, 3973-4005, 2021.
- [11] Bogdan V. Oaida, Amruta Yelamanchili, Christopher Wells, David R. Thompson, Robert O. Green, Matthew W. Bennett, Didier Keymeulen, Thang Pham, Daniel P. Poe, Lena Siskind, Charlene Ung, "Mapping Earth's Dust-Emitting Regions from the ISS with the EMIT Imaging Spectrometer" in IEEE Aerospace 2022
- [12] SDDR RH3440 Solid-State Data Recorder (#U SRIO VPX Radiation Tolerant SDDR): https://www.mrcy.com/application/files/5216/3001/4013/5008.22E_RH3440_3U_VPX_SRIO_SDDR.pdf
- [13] Low-complexity lossless and near-lossless multispectral and hyperspectral image compression. Report Concerning Space Data System Standards, CCSDS 123.0-B-2. Blue Book. Washington, D.C.: CCSDS, February 2019 [Online] (<https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/123x0b2c3.pdf>)
- [14] Alpha Data ADM-XRC-7z1 high performance reconfigurable XMC (compliant to VITA 42.0) based on the Xilinx Zynq range of Programmable System-on-Chips, <https://www.alpha-data.com/product/adm-xrc-7z1/>